

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

A test and evaluation program was conducted by General Dynamics/Space Systems Division under independent research and development funding to determine the damage susceptibility and damage tolerance of composite sandwich panels. Damage susceptibility and tolerance have been identified as critical issues in certifying composite materials for aerospace components. To address this concern, forty sandwich panels were fabricated, impacted, inspected and tested for residual strength. These panels used high strength graphite/epoxy face sheets and aluminum honeycomb core. These panels were impacted at energy levels sufficient to cause visible damage using an instrumented impact fixture. The resulting internal damage size was determined through ultrasonic inspection and residual strength was determined by testing the panels to failure under compression loads. The test matrix for this program was developed using a three factorial Box-Behnken design of experiments approach. The panel geometry and impact energy levels were used as the independent variables in this test matrix. The dependent variables were the resulting damage size and residual strength. This approach allowed damage size and residual strength to be determined as a function of panel geometry and impact energy and allowed data to be interpolated at intermediate points not covered in the test program.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Fiber, Graphite; Sandwich Construction; Damage Tolerance; Compression After Impact;

1. INTRODUCTION

A major area of concern in the application of advanced composite materials to aerospace structures is their sensitivity to low velocity impact damage. Current design criteria for composite structures on aerospace programs have evolved around the philosophy that structures have to be able to survive mission requirements in the presence of damage which is not detectable by visual inspection. Since composite materials can incur non-visible internal damage from low velocity impacts, this requires that the structure retain sufficient residual

strength after impact to survive operating loads. The primary method for insuring that structures have sufficient residual strength to meet this requirement is to reduce strain or strength design allowables to a level where undetected damage will not cause structural failure.

To determine the strength reductions required to meet these design criteria, a subcomponent test and evaluation program was conducted. This test program evaluated the effects of low velocity impact damage on structural integrity by fabricating and testing subcomponent panels representative of structures under study at General Dynamics. The test panels used in this program were composite sandwich constructions using high strength graphite/epoxy face sheets and metallic honeycomb core. Panels were fabricated, impacted at various energy levels, inspected, and tested to determine the effects of low velocity impact damage on structural integrity. The three major objectives of this test program were as follows:

- Establish quantifiable criteria for the definition of visible and non-visible damage.
- Establish the relationship of visible damage to associated non-visible damage.
- Establish the residual strength of composite structures at the visible damage threshold level.

This test program was conducted as a cooperative effort between the Space Systems and Fort Worth divisions of General Dynamics. Space Systems was responsible for panel fabrication and residual strength testing. Fort Worth performed the impact procedures and ultrasonic inspection for internal damage. The results of this program showed that at the defined visual damage threshold (2.54 mm indentation depth), the failure strain ranged from 4,000 to 5,000 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$. This was consistent with the strain levels currently being used in preliminary design studies and verified that these designs would be inherently damage tolerant.

2. SANDWICH PANEL DAMAGE TOLERANCE TEST PROGRAM

There were three major parts to the test program conducted during this study. An initial series of tests was performed to determine the impact energy that would create visible damage in the sandwich panels. This was determined by impacting test panels at increasing energy levels until the defined visual damage threshold (2.54 mm indentation depth) was achieved. The second series of tests impacted sandwich panels of different configurations at the defined visible damage threshold and tested these panels to failure to determine their residual strength. Three replicates were used for each test point during this series of tests to evaluate data scatter and provide a reasonable level of confidence in the resulting data. The final series of tests used the Box-Behnken advanced experimental design methodology. This technique allows for data to be interpolated between test points and allows the interaction between independent variables to be analytically studied. For this program, the independent variables were defined as the face sheet thickness, core thickness, and impact energy level. The derivation of the specific test points for this series of tests is discussed in Section 4.

The resulting matrix for these tests, which involved 40 panels of different configurations, is shown in Table 1. The nomenclature used in describing these panels is as follows:

- VD Panels used for determining visual damage threshold. Not tested for residual strength.
 Control Panels tested for failure load and strain in the undamaged condition.
 DT Panels tested for failure load and strain at the visual damage threshold.
 BB Panels tested as part of the Box-Behnken program to determine interaction effects.

TABLE 1. Sandwich Panel Damage Tolerance Test Matrix.

SPECIMEN I.D. #	IMPACT ENERGY N-m	CORE THICKNESS	FACE SHEET THICKNESS
		mm	# plies
VD-01	10.85	12.7	16
VD-02	13.56	12.7	16
VD-03	10.85	12.7	16
VD-04	12.20	12.7	16
VD-05	12.20	12.7	16
VD-06	10.31	25.4	16
VD-07	12.20	25.4	16
VD-08	12.20	25.4	16
VD-09	12.20	38.1	16
VD-10	13.98	38.1	16
VD-11	10.85	38.1	16
VD-12	8.14	38.1	16
VD-13	5.42	38.1	16
Control-01	0.00	12.7	8
Control-02	0.00	12.7	8
Control-03	0.00	12.7	8
DT-01	4.75	12.7	8
DT-02	4.75	12.7	8
DT-03	4.75	12.7	8
DT-04	8.48	25.4	12
DT-05	8.48	25.4	12
DT-06	8.48	25.4	12
DT-07	12.20	38.1	16
DT-08	12.20	38.1	16
DT-09	12.20	38.1	16
BB-01	8.48	38.1	16
BB-02	4.75	38.1	12
BB-03	12.20	38.1	12
BB-04	8.48	38.1	8
BB-05	4.75	25.4	16
BB-06	12.20	25.4	16
BB-07	8.48	25.4	12
BB-08	8.48	25.4	12
BB-09	8.48	25.4	12
BB-10	4.75	25.4	8
BB-11	12.20	25.4	8
BB-12	8.48	12.7	16
BB-13	4.75	12.7	12
BB-14	12.20	12.7	12
BB-15	8.48	12.7	8

2.1 Test Specimen Design The test specimen geometry, shown in Figure 1, was based upon the requirements of NASA RP 1092, ST-1, "Specification for Compression After Impact Test". This specification was originally designed for thick (6.35 mm) laminates and did not cover sandwich panels like those used during this test program. However, its guidelines provided a starting point for this project's specimen design and test procedures. The plan form area of all specimens was held constant. The face sheet and core thicknesses were varied as shown in Table 1.

A high strength, graphite/epoxy unidirectional tape material system was used for the face sheets. This system consisted of Amoco T-300 carbon fiber impregnated with the Fiberite 934 resin system. The adhesive used to bond the face sheets to the core was a 177°C cure epoxy film adhesive (Hysol EA 9684) for all panels with the exception of several preliminary panels used for determining visible/non-visible threshold. The core consisted of Hexcel 4.76 mm cell size, 32.0 kg/m³ density, aluminum honeycomb. The layouts of the face sheets, shown in Table 2, were varied according to thicknesses required at different test points.

FIGURE 1. Compression After Impact Specimen.

TABLE 2. Sandwich Panel Face Sheet Laminates.

NUMBER OF PLIES	FACE SHEET THICKNESS mm	LAMINATE LAYUP	% 0° PLIES	% ±45° PLIES	% 90° PLIES
8	1.06	[45/135/0/90]s	25	50	25
12	1.58	[45/135/0/90/45/135]s	16	68	16
16	2.11	[45/135/0/90]s	25	50	25

2.2 Test Specimen Fabrication The sandwich panels were fabricated using a non-autoclave cure process. This process involved precompacting, but not curing, the skins prior to mating them with the honeycomb core. The precompaction and final cure were accomplished using vacuum pressure only. The face sheets were fabricated by hand laying the unidirectional graphite/epoxy tape material into the specified pattern. This stack was placed upon an electrically heated plate which was in a sealed chamber. The chamber was evacuated to an absolute pressure of about 25 mm of mercury, allowing the air and volatile materials to escape while the stack was being heated past the point where the resin was freely flowing but prior to the onset of gelation. The stack was then compacted by allowing atmospheric pressure back into the chamber to force a membrane (vacuum bag) down on to the evacuated stack. This allowed the compaction of the plies and the softened resin with no void-forming gasses in the system. Once this compaction was accomplished, the system was cooled by chilling the support plate. The resin then solidified to a thermoplastic state, maintaining the compacted, void-free condition of the laminate. The sandwich panels were fabricated by assembling the precompacted skins, a film adhesive, and the honeycomb core and then cocuring the adhesive and the skins to the core under a vacuum bag in an oven at 177° C. Micro-graphs of the resulting components showed there was no discernible porosity or delamination in this component and the quality was equivalent to that expected for an autoclave cured component.

2.3 Impact Testing The impact testing of the specimens was performed using an instrumented system available at General Dynamics/Fort Worth Division. The impact apparatus consisted of a Dynatup model 8200 drop weight tower with a 12.7 mm diameter, 1.2-kg impacting tup and a Dynatup 730 data acquisition system. The specimens were held in place by a clamping plate during impacting to insure a uniform condition for all specimens. The impact energy was controlled by varying the drop height. The data acquisition system measured the velocity of the impactor and provided force-time and energy-time plots for the impact event.

2.4 Inspection After impacting, the specimens were inspected to determine the indentation depth and ultrasonically inspected to measure the internal damage area. This inspection was performed at Fort Worth using an ultrasonic scan system which consisted of a motorized immersion test tank and a Kraut/Craemer KB6000 pulser/receiver. C-scans of the impacted panels were performed in the pulse-echo mode, using a 9.53 mm diameter 5 MHz focussed transducer with a 50.8 mm focal/length. The analog C-scans were used to map the extent of the impact damage. The largest delamination was measured by focussing the transducer on a reflector just behind the back surface of the impacted laminate and gating at that location. Any damage in the laminate in front of the reflector would then result in a reduction of the ultrasonic signal at the gate location. Output consisted of a wet pen on/off paper plot. The damage threshold was established by making trial runs using a piece of lead tape of known geometry as a marker.

2.5 Residual Strength Testing The specimens were trimmed to a 127 mm by 254 mm size and potted into aluminum C-channels for residual strength testing. This testing was performed at Space Systems division using a 222 kN MTS system. The loading rate was 1.27 mm/minute. Digital readings of load from a single load cell and strain from gauges on each side of the specimen were measured at 5 second intervals. Maximum load was also automatically recorded by the data acquisition system.

3. TEST DATA SUMMARY

The test data measured for each panel included indentation depth, damage area, and failure strain. Figure 2 shows the indentation depth for the visual damage specimens as a function of impact energy. The indentation depth follows a fairly uniform pattern. The initial criteria defined for visible damage for this program was a 0.254 mm indentation depth. During the initial impact testing it was discovered that through penetration of the impacted face sheet would occur before this depth was reached as a smooth indentation. For the 16 ply face sheets, through penetration was occurring at approximately 12.20 N-m. For the 8 ply face sheets, through penetration was occurring at 4.75 N-m. These impact energy levels were established as the damage tolerance points at which to determine residual strength and strain to failure. These values were also used to define the impact energies for the Box-Behnken test matrix.

The load/strain behavior of the specimens tested for residual strength were typically linear to failure with only minor discrepancies between the strain gauges on the damaged and undamaged sides. A typical load/strain plot is shown in Figure 3. This behavior was expected and indicated that there were no premature failures due to specimen buckling or local delamination occurring. Examination of the failed specimens determined that all failures occurred as clean breaks starting at the impact damage zone and preceding horizontally across the specimen. The damage resulting from these failures was confined to a narrow band (12.7 mm wide) with no indications of delamination or debonding outside of the failure band. Typically, the inner ply on the face sheet stayed firmly bonded to the core.

Figure 4 shows the failure strain for the control, damage tolerance, and Box-Behnken specimens. The failure strain for the damaged specimens ranged from 4,000 to 5,000 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$ for all but two specimens. This would be consistent with what was expected for the 934 resin which is a non-toughened system. The specimens which failed below 4,000 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$ had 8 ply face sheets and were impacted at a level well beyond their visual damage threshold. The result was fairly extensive damage which would be readily detectable under service conditions and repaired before the structure was used. The relationship of failure strain to the impact energy ratio (test impact energy / visual damage threshold impact energy) is shown in Figure 5. Figure 6 shows the effect of laminate orientation on the failure strain. The 12 ply face sheets had a higher percentage of ± 45 plies which resulted in a lower modulus. This laminate was less sensitive to impact damage and had a higher strain to failure.

FIGURE 2. Dent Depth vs Impact Energy, Visual Damage Panels.

FIGURE 3. Typical Load/Strain Plot .

FIGURE 4. Failure Strain vs Impact Energy.

FIGURE 5. Failure Strain vs Impact Energy Ratio.

FIGURE 6. Failure Strain vs Face Sheet Thickness.

4. ADVANCED EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The Box-Behnken method is a multi-variable experimental design strategy, based on the factorial response polynomial approach, which enables identification of key variables and interactions as well as prediction of system response for combinations of variable parameters not tested. This method is based on a subset of the three-level factorial approach and enables examining the nonlinear functional relationship between a certain dependent response and high and low levels of various independent variables. Equation 1 illustrates the general form of the Box-Behnken response surface polynomial.

$$Y_{out} = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_{11}X_1^2 + b_{22}X_2^2 + b_{33}X_3^2 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{23}X_2X_3 \quad (1)$$

The Y_{out} term in Equation 1 represents the dependent response function term (i.e., indentation depth, damage area or residual strength for our test program) and the X_i values, are the values

of independent parameters (i.e., core thickness, number of plies, and impact energy for this study) scaled non-dimensionally such that +1 represents the highest level of the parameter and -1 represents the lowest level value of the parameter (a value of zero indicates an average value for the parameter). The coefficients b_0 , b_i , and b_{ij} are termed regression coefficients and are obtained from the results of experimental tests conducted in a specific manner. A three-variable Box-Behnken experimental design would require 15 tests to be run with the specific combinations of independent parameter levels shown in Table 3. The corresponding variable levels and non-dimensional independent parameters (+1,0,-1) are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 3. Box-Behnken Specimen Test Configuration.

SPECIMEN I.D.#	CORE THICKNESS	FACE SHEET THICKNESS	IMPACT ENERGY
BB-01	+1	+1	0
BB-02	+1	0	-1
BB-03	+1	0	+1
BB-04	+1	-1	0
BB-05	0	+1	-1
BB-06	0	+1	+1
BB-07	0	0	0
BB-08	0	0	0
BB-09	0	0	0
BB-10	0	-1	-1
BB-11	0	-1	+1
BB-12	-1	+1	0
BB-13	-1	0	-1
BB-14	-1	0	+1
BB-15	-1	-1	0

TABLE 4. Box-Behnken Variable Levels and Non-Dimensional Parameters.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES			VARIABLE LEVELS		
			LOW (-1)	AVERAGE (0)	HIGH (+1)
X_1	Core Thickness	mm	12.7	25.4	38.1
X_2	Face Sheet Thickness	no. of plies	8	12	16
X_3	Impact Energy	N-m	4.75	8.48	12.20

The values of the coefficients of the equations describing the response of the test panels for indentation depth, damage area, and failure load are summarized in Table 5. The strongest effects for the response of the test panels were from the impact energy and face sheet thickness which was expected. Figure 7 compares the plot for damage area for a 25.4 mm core generated from these coefficients with the results of test data.

TABLE 5. Box-Behnken Response Polynomial Coefficients.

PARAMETER	INDENTATION DEPTH mm	DAMAGE AREA mm ²	FAILURE LOAD kN
b ₀	2.591	354.8	92.20
b ₁ Core Thickness	0.025	-32.9	-0.40
b ₂ Face Sheet Thickness	-1.194	-54.2	39.91
b ₃ Impact Energy	1.118	62.6	-6.37
b ₁₁ Core Thickness	0.076	85.2	0.00
b ₂₂ Face Sheet Thickness	-0.229	24.5	-2.21
b ₃₃ Impact Energy	-0.330	-38.7	7.37
b ₁₂ Core Thickness Face Sheet Thickness	0.000	148.4	-1.01
b ₁₃ Core Thickness Impact Energy	-0.051	21.9	-3.73
b ₂₃ Face Sheet Thickness Impact Energy	-0.051	18.1	-2.96

FIGURE 7. Damage Area (25.4 mm core) Calculated From Box-Behnken Coefficients.

5. BIOGRAPHY

Craig Rix graduated from Iowa State University in 1981 with a B.S. in Civil Engineering. In 1985, he joined General Dynamics and since that time has provided analytical and technical support to IRAD, CRAD, project, and proposal activities. His experience has included coordinating the activities of design, analysis, materials and processes, and manufacturing technology personnel in developing design concepts for aerospace structures. This work has included organizing and conducting test programs to evaluate the behavior of composite materials and structures.